

Energy doing work formula and energy intensity

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Abstract: In each closed three-way equilibrium system, all the energy grows in the internal infinite cycle of the system. Since there is no absolute independence in any system, the interaction between the system and the system is actually a relationship of "energy work" between the systems. The "energy work" here is the concept of "energy" in traditional physics.

Key words: energy; work; energy work; energy work between system and system;

Introduction

The action force (the resultant force of the object) acts on the object, making the "energy doing work" (energy conversion between systems), which is actually related to the "action time", "action force" and "energy doing power".

1 Energy does the work formula

1.1 Energy work

The action force (the resultant force of the object) acts on the object, so that the "energy work" of the movement of the object is actually the "action time" multiplied by the quadratic of the "action force" and multiplied by the "energy does power".

That is, the energy does the work formula: 能量做功 = $(F \cdot t)^2 \cdot 50\%$ (做功率)

1.2 Formula derivation process

We imagine a stationary 1 kg mass object in a weight environment (completely free of any other force), suddenly subjected by a 1 Newtonian-sized force that obtains an acceleration of 1m/s.

After 1s, the speed of the object movement becomes 1m/s, with a total moving distance of 0.5m, or 0.5J.

When 2s, the speed of the object motion becomes 2m/s and the total distance of movement is 2m, or 2J.

When 3s, the speed of the object becomes 3m/s with a total distance of 4.5m, or 4.5J.

When 4s, the speed of object movement becomes 4m/s and the total distance of movement is 8m, or 8J.

By substituting these data into the "energy work formula", do you find that the resulting "energy work" (the "energy" in traditional physics) is exactly the same as the above conclusion?

1.2 Why is the energy doing power 50%?

Why in the "energy power" formula, energy power is 50%, not what other value?

This is because in the "ternary balance system", the role and influence between the system (also the internal of the larger system) is all accomplished through the mutual energy (unit time force), and "energy work" for the system itself, is only a relative concept of the action between the system and the system.

So we can assume that when one side of the object completely free from other forces is suddenly subjected to a 1 Newton-sized force, and on the other side of the object is a wall (an obstacle to the movement), the object is actually squeezed by the force in two directions.

So the "unit time force" (energy), actually all acting on the system of the object, will form a change effect on the system of the object (including the deformation caused by the object due to pressure, etc.). In this state, the object is subject to both force, so the energy do power is 0%.

But when the wall suddenly disappears, then the object is only subject to a working force in one direction, which also forms a changing effect on the object's internal system. In this state, the object is only subject to one acting force, so the energy do power is 50%.

In the natural system "energy power", there are three states, the first is that the force does not do work, the energy power is 0%.

The second is that the force does work (where the resultant work received by the object) and the energy doing power is equal to or less than 50% (without considering the influence of the internal resistance phenomenon of the ternary equilibrium system. High-speed motion considers the influence of the internal resistance of the ternary equilibrium system, and the energy doing power is less than 50%. That is, this energy, doing power, decreases as the object moves faster).

The third is that the energy doing power is 100% (e. g., the energy produced by nuclear fusion, which is 100% is constant).

2 Formula in Traditional Physics

2.1 Contradiction between Traditional Physical Formulae

Everyone must have in the mind such a question! That is, the formula for doing work in traditional physics is $W=FS$.

That is, also in a weightlessness environment (completely without any other force), when the mass of the object becomes 10kg, suddenly subjected to 1N size, the object obtains an acceleration of 0.1m/s, and after 1s the object moves by a distance of 0.05 meters.

If the traditional formula for work done in physics is $W=Fs$ or $E= (1 / 2) mv^2$, the work done is 0.05J. But if you follow the energy work formula $E= (1 / 2)F^2 t^2$ calculation, the work is still 0.5J, why does this happen?

2.2 Effective work performance is related to the object quality

This is because the work relationship between energy in the system and the system should also be related to the quality of the object. The same speed of the moving object, the greater the mass of the greater kinetic energy. The force acts on the object, the acceleration related to the

mass of the object.

That is, the formula for doing work in traditional physics is that $W=Fs$ and $E= (1 / 2) mv^2$ are not correct. Why say that?

First, $W=Fs$, when an object with its own initial velocity, if suddenly encountered a force to slow it, at the same time to apply a force to cancel the deceleration, to maintain the original initial speed. Neither of these forces produces really effective work (It will only work on inside the object system. For example, Cause ject deformation), but in the view of $W=FS$, the work formula in traditional physics, both forces do work to the object, one positive work and the other negative work.

This situation is actually the effect of object inertia, and the two reciprocal forces only maintain the original inertial motion of the object.

For example, the earth rotates from west to east, when a man pushes a wall hard east. The earth moves through rotation, and then the wall will actually shift accordingly with the earth's rotation. But the man pushed the wall eastward, and its force did not produce effective work. Therefore, only when the resultant force exerted by the object acts on the object can it produce effective work.

2.3 Effective work formula

So, the effective work formula should be that $W=Fs$, F is the size of the resultant force that the object receives, s is the moving distance, and m is the mass of the object.

For example, a 10kg object, subject to a resultant force of 1N. The resultant force of the object is not 0, then the object will inevitably produce acceleration or deceleration, the change in speed, is the effective work of the acting force. No change in speed, in fact, is not a role of a certain force.

3 The New Concept of Physics, "Energy Strength"

3.1 Energy intensity

In traditional physics, the kinetic energy formula $E= (1 / 2) mv^2$, is not actually correct. The right thing is $E= (1 / 2) m^2 v^2$, with a new concept, energy intensity, is simply discussed here.

"Energy intensity" is the degree of change (destruction) formed by the energy transfer between the system and the system. However, the concept of kinetic energy in traditional physics actually has a certain intersection with the new physical concept of "energy intensity". If the "energy intensity" is removed from the traditional kinetic energy formula, then it should be $E= (1 / 2) m^2 v^2$.

3.2 Energy intensity formula

"Energy intensity" formula: $\text{能量烈度} = \frac{F \times t}{\sqrt{t_0}}$, where F is the size of the resultant force for the object acceleration, t is the time the force F gives the object acceleration, and t_0 is the contact time when the object hits the other objects after the object obtains the kinetic energy.

In traditional physics, the cognition of the size of the kinetic energy of objects actually covers part of the concept of "energy intensity". For example, a 1kg object hits other objects at 10m/s, 10 times as a 10kg object at 1m/s, $E = (1/2)mv^2$.

But in fact, this is because the contact time of an object impact (namely t_0 in the "energy intensity formula") varies with results of different "energy intensity" sizes presented. The faster the object speed, the contact time of impact will become shorter, the contact time of impact will become shorter, and the "energy intensity" generated by the impact will increase.

3.3 Energy intensity size and energy size

In traditional physics, because there is no concept of "energy intensity", so in some places, the size of "energy intensity" and the energy size are actually confused together. It is then assumed that the effect of object velocity of motion on kinetic energy is greater than object mass on kinetic energy, hence the formula like $E = (1/2)mv^2$.

3.4 Energy doing work formula and new kinetic energy formula

The corrected kinetic energy formula $E = (1/2)m^2v^2$ and the energy doing work formula $E = (Ft)^2 * 50%$, E both represent energy (energy work), which is $(1/2)m^2v^2 = (Ft)^2 * 50%$, so can also be simplified as $(1/2)m^2v^2 = (1/2)F^2t^2$, further gives the momentum formula: $Ft = mv$.

Where F is the resultant force of the object received, t is the time used by the acting force F to accelerate the object, m is the mass of the object, and v is the last obtained velocity of the object.

The energy transfer between the system and the system is essentially a transfer of " Ft ", and the object mass and velocity (mv), are just the two states of energy (relevant theory 《三元平衡定律》)。

3.5 Conversion of potential energy and kinetic energy

It can also be written as $(E = (2)m^2v^2 = (1/2)F^2t^2 = Fsm$. by $E = (Ft)^2 * 50%$ and $E = (1/2)m^2v^2$, $W = Fsm$

Where $Fsm = (1/2)m^2v^2$, can also be used to represent the conversion relationship of potential energy and kinetic energy. s is the distance (height) where the object falls freely, F is the gravity received when the object falls freely, and m is the mass of the object.

4 The "energy doing work formula" is verified through related experiments

4.1 A "special Newtonian pendulum experiment"

This experiment is the "Newton pendulum experiment of different quality", and the Newton pendulum used in the experiment is slightly different from the traditional Newton pendulum, and

the difference is that the Newton pendulum ball is of different masses.

In this new Newtonian pendulum, the quality of A and B pendulum is different. We assume that the quality of A pendulum is $m=2\text{kg}$, and that of B pendulum ball is $(1/2)m=1\text{kg}$. If the A pendulum is released from high places and hits the B pendulum at $v = 1 \text{ m/s}$, the B pendulum gets a speed after the impact, which we assume is v_2 . While the A pendulum ball slows down under the impact, we assume that the speed of the A pendulum ball after hitting the B pendulum ball is v_1 .

4.2 The formula of the momentum theorem conflicts the (original) kinetic energy formula

So based on the momentum conservation, we can know that $mv=mv_1+0.5mv_2$. However, if we still follow the original kinetic energy formula ($E= (1/2)mv^2$), according to the law of energy conservation, we get $(1/2)mv^2= (1/2)mv_1^2 + 0.5(1/2)mv_2^2$. We bring each value ($m=2\text{kg}$, $v = 1 \text{ m/s}$) into the two equations.

It is concluded that $mv_1^2 + 0.5mv_2^2 = 2$ and $mv_1 + 0.5mv_2 = 2$, after a simple mathematical calculation, the only conditions for the two equations to hold can only be, $v_1 = 1 \text{ m/s}$, $v_2 = 0 \text{ m/s}$. This conclusion is obviously seriously inconsistent with the actual situation of the experiment, so it can be proved that the conservation of momentum ($mv=mv_1+0.5mv_2$) and the original kinetic energy formula ($E= (1/2)mv^2$), one two must be wrong.

4.3 Further find out the trap of scientific logic

In this trial, as long as the A and the B pendulum balls collide, regardless

of the final speed v_1 and the B pendulum ball obtain the velocity v_2 , as long as it is not $v_1 = 1$ m/s and the $mv_1^2 + 0.5mv_2^2 = 2$ and $mv_1 + 0.5mv_2 = 2$ m/s $v_2 = 0$ m/s (without any collision).

In that is to words, in the process of collision, we can first assume that there is no conversion to internal energy (kinetic energy loss), then the two equations of $mv_1^2 + 0.5mv_2^2 = 2$ and $mv_1 + 0.5mv_2 = 2$ can not hold at the same time. In fact, after the collision of the pendulum ball of different masses, the so-called "part of the kinetic energy will transform into the internal energy (kinetic energy loss)" is actually a logical trap created to cover up its contradictory scientific facts.

Two pendulum balls of equal mass, two swing balls impact speed exchange, why don't "kinetic energy convert into internal energy"? Why do two swing balls of different qualities, even if the material used is exactly the same as before, mean that "a part of the kinetic energy is converted into internal energy"? After our cognitive thinking, it is easier to see this obvious trap of scientific logic.

pendulum ball, there is no loss of kinetic energy, and finally the A pendulum ball speed is $v_1 = 0.5$, and the B pendulum ball speed is $v_2 = 1$, so that the conservation of kinetic energy is $mv^2 = mv_1^2 + 0.5mv_2^2 = 2$, but if you take the momentum theorem formula into it, it must be $mv_1 + 0.5mv_2 = 2$.

the law of energy conservation and momentum conservation must have an error. It is clear that the law of conservation of energy and the law of conservation of momentum is absolutely not wrong, then the wrong must be the original kinetic energy formula $E = (1/2)mv^2$.

Therefore, it can be further explained that the conservation of momentum ($mv = mv_1 + 0.5mv_2$) and the law of conservation of energy and the original kinetic energy formula ($E = (1/2)mv^2$) must be one is wrong.

4.4 Correct the wrong (original) kinetic energy formula with the corrected kinetic energy formula

However, if we correct the original kinetic energy formula ($E = (1/2)mv^2$) to the new kinetic energy formula ($E = (1/2)m^2v^2$), the calculation results will fully match the experimental situation, so we can verify that the original kinetic energy formula ($E = (1/2)mv^2$) is the wrong formula with missing or wrong physical meaning.

5. Conclusion

Through the interpretation of "energy does work" (which is also the concept of energy in the traditional physics), it is actually to be able to better explain the concept of energy in the ternary equilibrium system. In other words, energy circulates inside the "ternary balance system". The

energy transfer between the system and the system is essentially a kind of "unit time force" (Ft) transfer, and the mass and speed (mv) of an object are only two states presented by the energy.

Literature:

[1] 《三元平衡定律》 : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4539809>

The English version is converted by translation software, so there may be many translation errors.